

Conference Abstract

The Great British Hedgerow Survey

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Abstract

In 2013, when the dormouse reintroduction protocol was revised, a national hedge survey methodology was available. This survey enabled individual hedge quality to be assessed and from that, it was possible to quantify the quality of landscape links between reintroduction sites. There was an opportunity to build on this survey so that it could be used more widely and have more useful outcomes. The People's Trust for Endangered Species (PTES) acquired the existing data from the national (DEFRA) survey and started to develop a survey methodology that would be compatible with it, be simple to use, provide a report on the existing state of the hedgerow and give management advice on how to maintain the hedgerow in good condition. As part of the survey development, posters were designed. One of these asks: 'What have hedgerows ever done for us', to demonstrate the benefit of hedgerows in the landscape. The other shows 'The hedgerow management cycle' to highlight the dynamic nature of hedgerow condition. There are two different hedgerow surveys available, each with a slightly different focus and outcomes. *Healthy Hedgerows* is a rapid hedgerow survey designed for landowners that want to create a hedge management plan. *The Great British Hedgerow Survey* generates more detailed feedback on hedgerow health and offers management advice. It is particularly suited to volunteer groups. This talk will discuss the development of the surveys and their part in hedgerow protection in the UK in the future.

Keywords

hedge, hedgerow, survey, landscape connectivity

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